

HEALTH ECONOMICS ANALYSIS PLAN (HEAP)

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Decide-TB project

Version 3.0

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List of abbreviations

ART	Antiretroviral Therapy
CEA	Cost-effectiveness analysis
CREDIM	Centre de Recherche et Développement en Informatique Médicale
CXR	Chest radiography or Chest X-ray
DALYs	Disability-Adjusted Life Years
DH	District Hospital
DR	Digital Radiography
GA	Gastric Aspirate
HC	Health Centre
HCW	Health Care Workers
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
ICER	Incremental Cost-Effectiveness Ratio
IRD	Institut de Recherche pour le Développement (Research Institute for Development)
MOH	Ministry of Health
NPA	Nasopharyngeal aspirate
NTP	National Tuberculosis Programme
OPD	Outpatients Department
PAANTHER	Paediatric Asian African Network for Tuberculosis and HIV Research
PHC	Primary Health Centre
PI	Principal Investigator
RIF	Rifampicin
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
SAM	Severe Acute Malnutrition
SOC	Standard of Care
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TB	Tuberculosis
TDA	Treatment Decision Algorithm
UBx	University of Bordeaux
WHO	World Health Organization

Section 1: Administrative Information

1.1 HEAP Administrative Information

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1.2 Signature page

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1.3 History of HEAP versions

Version No.	Version Date	Amendment Summary
1.0	31/05/2024	Original version
2.0	04/10/2024	Revisions requested by EDCTP
3.0	24/03/2026	Within-trial CEA approach described

Section 2: Trial Introduction & Background

2.1 Trial Background and Rationale

WHO has conditionally recommended in March 2022, the use of treatment decision algorithms (TDAs) to diagnose pulmonary tuberculosis (TB) in children below 10 years (World Health Organization 2022). The National TB Programs (NTPs) of Mozambique and Zambia have decided to implement, in a programmatic pilot, a comprehensive TDA-based approach for TB screening, diagnosis and management in children, as part of local adoption of the WHO's conditional recommendation (Decide-TB project 2023). The NTPs in both countries are working with researchers to implement this programmatic pilot in a way that provides comprehensive data on the effectiveness, acceptability, feasibility and cost-effectiveness of the new TDA-based approach to be collected. The collaboration between the NTPs of Mozambique and Zambia, together with researchers from Europe and Africa, forms the Decide TB consortium and the evaluation of the programmatic pilot is the Decide TB project. The TDAs being evaluated are: i) the WHO suggested TDA A (for settings with CXR available), ii) WHO TDA B (for settings without CXR), iii) the TB-Speed SAM TDA and iv) the PAANTHER TDA for children living with HIV, for use at secondary or primary healthcare level (**Figure 1**). A severity assessment is also included in the comprehensive approach where children classified as having non-severe disease will receive a 4-month regimen while the rest will receive 6-month treatment. The Decide-TB trial is a pragmatic cluster-randomised trial with a stepped wedge design aiming to provide scientific evidence on a comprehensive TDA-based approach (intervention) for TB screening, diagnostic and treatment in children less than 15 years at low levels of healthcare in Zambia and Mozambique. The intervention will be implemented as a programmatic pilot, as NTPs in Mozambique and Zambia have taken the decision to pilot the implementation of a TDA-based approach as part of local adoption of the WHO's conditional recommendation to do so. The outcomes of the trial will be documented by researchers.

Figure 1. TDAs used according to entry sites and populations (PHC or DH). *PHC: Primary Health Center; TDA: Treatment Decision Algorithm; CXR: chest X-ray; CLHIV: children living with HIV; SAM: severe acute malnutrition. Children hospitalised with SAM are not eligible for 4-month regimen and therefore not eligible for severity assessment.*

2.2 Aim of the Trial

The general objective of the Decide-TB trial is to assess the effectiveness, feasibility and implementation, acceptability, costs and cost-effectiveness, and adoption of a comprehensive TDA-based approach for childhood TB screening, diagnosis, and treatment decision-making piloted and implemented under programmatic conditions at DH and PHC level in Mozambique and Zambia.

2.3 Objectives of the trial

The following 5 specific objectives correspond to 5 research components: feasibility (implementation), effectiveness, acceptability, costs, and policy.

1. To assess the **effectiveness** of the comprehensive TDA-based approach in increasing TB case detection in children and providing good quality TB diagnosis and shorter treatment decision making (diagnostic accuracy and reliability of treatment decision for TB and shorter treatment), as compared to the standard of care (SOC).
2. To describe the **implementation** and the **feasibility** of using the comprehensive TDA-based approach, and to identify contextual determinants influencing implementation and contribute to improved implementation/adaptations throughout intervention delivery.
3. To assess **preferences, acceptability**, and perceived **feasibility** of using the comprehensive TDA-based approach among end-users, beneficiaries, and key stakeholders.
4. To assess the **costs** from the health system and the beneficiary (parents/caregivers of children) perspective, the **cost-effectiveness** of using the comprehensive TDA-based approach and the budget impact of scaling up the intervention.
5. To assess the factors and stakeholders that support or constrain the **adoption** of the comprehensive TDA-based approach as **health policy** at the district level.

2.4 Trial population

All sick children aged below 15 years entering the selected health facilities (DH and PHC) at either outpatient (OPD) or inpatient (IPD) departments, including children from high-risk groups, as well as children identified as contacts of TB cases through community- or facility-based household contact tracing.

Children with presumptive TB including children from high-risk groups with informed consent provided for data sharing for research within the NTP DHIS2 data collection tool.

Health care workers (nurses/clinicians, doctors, radiologists, radiographers, laboratory staff, community health workers) providing TB-related care services are also participants in the research activities.

2.5 Intervention and comparators

Intervention: The intervention consists of implementing a comprehensive TDA-based approach for TB diagnosis and treatment decision-making, including shorter treatment for non-severe TB in children identified as TB presumptive cases through a CDSS. It will also include the management of high-risk groups such as children living with HIV and SAM.

Comparator: The current standard of TB care that represents routine practice in Mozambique and Zambia.

2.6 Trial design

The Decide-TB trial is a pragmatic cluster-randomised trial with a stepped wedge design aiming to provide scientific evidence on a comprehensive Treatment Decision Algorithm (TDA)-based approach (intervention) for TB screening, diagnostic and treatment in children less than 15 years at low levels of healthcare in Zambia and Mozambique. The intervention will be implemented as a programmatic pilot, as National Tuberculosis Programs in Mozambique and Zambia have decided to pilot the implementation of a TDA-based approach as part of local adoption of the WHO's conditional recommendation to do so.

2.7 Trial start and end dates

The Decide-TB trial will start on May 2nd, 2024, and will end on April 30th, 2026, corresponding to a trial period of 2 years. At the point of the initial within-trial cost-effectiveness, data on diagnostic accuracy will not be available, as this requires additional clinical review work. Initial analyses will therefore not seek to model outcomes like mortality that depend strongly on true TB status.

Section 3: Economic Approach

3.1 Aims of economic evaluation

The aims are to assess the cost-effectiveness and the budget impact of the Decide-TB intervention (from the health care system's perspective), and its potential impact on reducing costs incurred by carers of children diagnosed with TB (beneficiaries' perspective).

3.2 Objectives of economic evaluation

There are 3 objectives for the Decide-TB economic evaluations.

1/ To conduct cost analyses of the SOC and of the comprehensive TDA-based approach:

- 1) Total TB care costs from the health system perspective
- 2) Unit cost per TB care activity (e.g. clinical assessment, CXR)
- 3) Total TB care costs of overdiagnosis and underdiagnosis - intervention only
- 4) Total costs incurred by parents/caregivers for receiving child TB care

2/ To evaluate the cost-effectiveness of the comprehensive TDA-based approach compared to the SOC (per child attending care and per child with presumptive TB):

1. Modelled health impact measure:
 - a. Number of children treated for TB
 - b. Number of adults treated for TB
 - c. Number of children treated for TB with a 6-month regimen
 - d. Number of children treated for TB with a 4-month regimen (following a severity assessment)
 - e. Number of deaths.
 - f. Disability-Adjusted Life Years (DALYs): a measure of healthy life lost, either through premature death or living with disability due to illness.
2. Cost-effectiveness measure i.e. incremental cost per:
 - a. Incremental number of children and adults treated for TB
 - b. Death averted
 - c. DALY averted

3/ To evaluate the budget impact of the comprehensive TDA-based approach scale-up compared to the SOC over 5 years:

1. Cost of scaling up the comprehensive TDA-based approach nationally
2. Cumulative number of children treated for TB, lives saved, and DALYs averted during a 5-year scale-up

3.3 Overview of economic analysis

The health system/provider costs, TB patient costs, and cost-effectiveness analyses are nested within the Decide-TB trial. The budget impact analysis, including costs of scaling up nationally will use trial and national (NTP, Ministry of Health) data. An initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will accompany the main trial reporting and focus on the incremental costs per additional child starting anti-TB treatment, comparing the intervention with SOC. When diagnostic accuracy data become available, subsequent model-based analyses will focus on cost-effectiveness in terms of incremental costs per DALY averted.

3.4 Legal/Policy framework

The trial is conducted in public health facilities in Mozambique and in Zambia, which are publicly funded, primarily free at the point of use.

3.5 Perspectives

The cost-effectiveness and budget impact analyses will take the perspective of the national healthcare systems. The patient cost survey will adopt the patient's perspective. The combination of all economic analyses will allow us to explore the overall benefits and costs of the Decide-TB intervention accounting from these two perspectives.

3.6 Time horizon

The initial within-trial CEA will use the costs associated with TB treatment, with no projection of outcomes or discounting of costs or outcomes. The subsequent model-based cost-effectiveness analyses will compare the costs and health outcomes of each arm extrapolated to a lifetime horizon using mathematical modelling to capture the full benefit of any differences in mortality between alternative interventions. The budget impact analysis will be conducted with time horizons of 1 year and 5 years.

Section 4: Economic Data Collection and Management

4.1 Statistical software use for health economic analysis

R software version 4.3.2 (or higher) will be used for data analysis including the within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis, and the patient cost survey, using *rstan* for hierarchical modelling. Microsoft Excel and R will be used for analysing costs and budget impact.

4.2 Identification of resources

The resources required by participants on each of the patient care pathways – corresponding to the SOC and the Decide-TB intervention – need to be enumerated. This includes both resources specific to individual patients, such as medication, as well as shared costs such as equipment which will be distributed equitably between all service users. Resource use specific to research only (such as study administration and additional follow-up visits) will be excluded to represent the costs expected in a routine non-study environment. Costs at scale will differentiate between fixed and variable costs to account for potential (dis)economies of scale. Allocation factors

(e.g. proportion of microbiological tests conducted for child TB vs adult TB diagnosis using a GeneXpert machine) will be applied to allocate shared costs (e.g. GeneXpert machine costs) to the Decide-TB intervention.

As this is a within-trial analysis, resource use in the model will be based directly upon the actual resource use of each patient within the Decide-TB intervention study.

Decide-TB is investigating strategies for improving the diagnosis of TB in children who have already sought health care at primary care facilities or hospitals. It is not investigating any strategies for increasing the number of children seeking health care. Therefore, it is not expected that the number of children presenting to health facilities will vary between the diagnostic interventions being assessed, but it is expected that the proportion of those patients who are diagnosed with TB will increase with the interventions. If a country adopts the Decide-TB intervention, it is expected that it would need to be implemented at the current existing health facilities. Consequently, the economic analyses will assume that only current facilities will be used, with no facilities being opened, enlarged, or closed as a result of a change in TB diagnostic strategy.

The cost analysis will account for the overhead costs (or above service level costs), following costing guidelines (Vassall et al. 2017). These comprise the overhead costs of running a health centre or hospital, such as buildings, furniture, administration and management, utilities, cleaning and security. These resources are shared amongst all the users of a facility. Similarly, there are shared costs of operating the infrastructure of a national health system and national TB programme. Therefore, the resource use and costs collected for the cost analysis will reflect the full total costs to the health system of diagnosing and treating each patient. Finally, the cost-effectiveness analysis will compare costs in the SOC and the intervention. The difference in costs between the SOC and the Decide-TB intervention (the incremental cost) will reflect the true incremental cost.

The cost of staffing will be included, in recognition that different diagnostic strategies may require more or less staff time, and if scaled up this could require a greater or lesser number of HCWs. We note that if an intervention would require increased staff numbers then the feasibility of this in practice would need to be considered alongside the cost effectiveness.

The cost-effectiveness and budget impact analyses use the perspective of the health service provider (Ministry of Health). Resource use falling upon patients, such as transportation and loss of earnings will be estimated in a separate analysis informed by the patient cost survey.

4.3 Measurement of resource use data

Table 1 below outlines the resource use data required and how they will be collected. The data will be collected using data collection tools designed for the project accompanied by detailed procedures (see Decide-TB Health Economics Data Collection SOP).

Table 1. Resource use data required

Type of resource	Information required	Sources	People involved
Consultations and appointments: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> initial presentation screening diagnosis check-up, etc. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of each consultation number and role(s) of HCW(s) involved consumable supplies, if any required (e.g. gloves) 	Patient care pathways	Pathways developed by health economists from interviews with study HCWs
Diagnostic tests <ul style="list-style-type: none"> NPA stool sputum CXR blood tests 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of each test consumable supplies/kit required for each test number and role(s) of HCW(s) involved in taking sample number and role(s) of laboratory staff involved in testing sample 	Patient care pathways	Pathways developed by health economists from interviews with study HCWs
Medications <ul style="list-style-type: none"> each drug dispensed 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> name of drug dosage and frequency duration of treatment 	Patient care pathways, National treatment guidelines	Pathways developed by health economists from interviews with study HCWs
Hospitalization <ul style="list-style-type: none"> inpatient stays medications for comorbidities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of hospital stays duration of stay drug name, dosage and duration of treatment 	Patient care pathways	Pathways developed by health economists from interviews with study HCWs
Major equipment, e.g. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> X-ray machine GeneXpert machine 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> number of items annual number of uses disaggregated by populations of interest (adults, children, vulnerable groups for child TB) expected lifetime of item 	Facility and Decide-TB records; supplier information	Records obtained by SSRAs and health economists from facility managers, project managers and suppliers
Labour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> length of time spent by each HCW on each activity, such as <ul style="list-style-type: none"> consultation taking sample use of digital tools length of time spent by each HCW on training 	Timesheets (Time and motion study) Decide-TB project training schemes	Timesheets completed by study HCWs and lab staff; data analysed by health economists CPMs will assist SSRAs and health economists in identifying sources
Family resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> time loss, food 	Patient cost survey	SSRA and health economists

4.4 Valuation of resource use data

Price data will be collected in each country to provide a unit cost for each resource used. **Table 2** below outlines the cost data that will be collected and the collection methods. The data will be collected using data collection tools designed for the project accompanied by detailed procedures (SOP). The data collection tools will be adapted from the Value TB costing tool suite developed in conjunction with the Global Health Cost Consortium (GHCC), with reference to the GHCC/WHO guidance ‘Costing Guidelines for Tuberculosis Interventions’ (World Health Organization, 2019).

The following sections explain the different methods for collecting cost data.

Table 2. Cost data required

Type of cost	Information required	Sources	People involved
Labour	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Staff employment costs: salary + additional employer costs Guardian’s loss of income 	National pay scales; project accounts Patient cost survey	Financial managers and NTP coordinator will assist SSRAs and health economists in identifying sources
Medications	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit cost of each drug preparation 	Published sources (national price lists, manufacturer price lists), internal sources (project accounts, invoices)	Financial managers and NTP coordinator will assist SSRAs and health economists in identifying sources
Consumables (including materials for diagnostic tests)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit cost of each item 	Published sources (national price lists, manufacturer price lists), internal sources (project accounts, invoices)	Financial managers and NTP coordinator will assist SSRAs and health economists in identifying sources
Equipment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit cost of equipment Cost of installation and maintenance 	Project accounts	Financial managers
Hospitalization	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Unit cost of an inpatient bed day 	WHO-CHOICE unit cost estimates for service delivery	Health economists
Other costs incurred to families	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Costs of transport, food, additional drugs 	Patient cost survey	SSRAs

4.5 Identification of outcomes

The primary outcome measure for the initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will be the proportion of children starting anti-TB treatment from those attending care. The primary outcome measure for the subsequent cost-effectiveness analyses will be DALYs.

4.6 Measurement of outcomes

Outcomes for the initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will be as for the trial primary analysis, i.e. numerators/denominators for each country, district, and quarter (by arm) of children starting anti-TB treatment out of those attending care. We will analyse each country separately, and in common with the main trial analyses, present additionally-stratified analyses depending on which data are available at the time of analysis: children age <1, children with SAM, CLHIV, children presenting at DH, children presenting at PHC.

DALYs will be quantified according to the WHO and Global Burden of Disease definition, as the sum of the years of life lost due to premature mortality in the population and the years lived with disability for people living with the health condition or its consequences (World Health Organization 2019). To estimate DALYs, the projected life expectancy, TB prevalence and the Global Burden of Disease disability weights will be applied to the TB disease states in the model. The remaining life expectancy will be estimated using each country's age- and sex-specific life table estimates. Age weighting will not be adopted. Following the end of treatment, patients will be assumed to return to normal health, taking account of TB-related morbidity and other long-term comorbidities such as HIV.

Other outcomes such as number of children treated for TB (6-month or 4-month regimen), number of deaths will be modelled based on the Decide-TB trial data.

4.7 Valuations of outcomes

The data required to calculate DALYs will be derived from data collected during the Decide-TB study, from countries' national available data sources or the published literature. Mortality data will be estimated using data from the study and from reviewing the literature. Life expectancy will be extracted from national life expectancy tables and disability weights will be taken from WHO Global Burden Estimates calculations (World Health Organization 2020).

Section 5: Economic Data Analysis

5.1 Analysis population

The cost and cost-effectiveness analyses will be based on "intention to treat" (ITT) strategy including all randomised participants. The patient cost survey will include parents/caregivers of children diagnosed with TB from the sites included in the Decide-TB trial.

5.2 Timing of analyses

The economic analysis will be performed at the end of the two-year period of the trial. The initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will be performed alongside the main trial analysis. Subsequent model-based cost-effectiveness analyses will be performed once diagnostic accuracy data are available to properly model mortality outcomes in calculating DALYs.

Figure 2. Decide-TB stepped wedge trial phases

5.3 Discount rates for costs and benefits

The initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis, both costs and benefits accrue within a 1 year time frame and so will not be discounted.

In the subsequent cost-utility analyses, both the costs and DALYs calculated in the extrapolation of the cost-effectiveness modelling will be discounted at an annual rate of 3% as recommended by WHO-CHOICE and the iDSI Reference Case for Economic Evaluation (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Sensitivity analysis will examine the impact of varying the discount rates in countries where higher discount rates are considered locally appropriate.

5.4 Cost-effectiveness thresholds

The initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will not use cost-effectiveness thresholds for comparison as these are not available for units of incremental cost per treatment initiation. Subsequent model-based cost-utility analyses will make reference to thresholds.

The subsequent cost-utility economic analyses will use the mid-points of the published country-specific estimates of opportunity-cost-based cost-effectiveness thresholds (Revill et al. 2020; Ochalek et al. 2018; Woods et al. 2016). The ICER results calculated by the modelling will be compared with the threshold for the relevant country to assess whether implementing the intervention(s) is likely to be a cost-effective use of available resources within the health care budget for that country – that is, that diverting resources to this new intervention would

increase health for the population as a whole to a greater extent than the opportunity cost of the health care foregone by reducing resources elsewhere in the health system.

Country-specific cost-effectiveness thresholds will be presented to decision-makers at the NTPs (or Ministry of Health) for feedback on their relevance and accuracy in the priority setting process. We will invite decision-makers' suggestions of alternative criteria to define 'locally relevant' cost-effectiveness threshold. We will use cost-effectiveness acceptability curves, measuring the probability of cost-effectiveness against a defined threshold, to present the uncertainty around our ICER estimates.

5.5 Statistical decision rules

The mean differences in costs, proportions initiating treatment and DALYs between the treatment groups will be estimated with associated 95% uncertainty intervals.

5.6 Analysis of resource use

Differences in resource use between randomised groups will be described, but not be compared statistically.

5.7 Analysis of healthcare system costs

Mean costs (total costs and disaggregated costs) between arms will be calculated and reported descriptively alongside their 95% uncertainty intervals, but not be compared statistically. Cost analyses will be conducted following the WHO guidelines (World Health Organization, 2019). Total and unit cost per child will be examined by country, by subgroups such as vulnerable children living with HIV and/or SAM, type of cost inputs, type of TB care activity, and by type of health facility (DH versus PHC), as per the main trial and Section 4.6.

5.8 Analysis of cost-effectiveness

The initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will use a bivariate Bayesian hierarchical model to simultaneously model costs and outcomes (Gomes et al. 2012). Outcome data will comprise numerator and denominator counts by country, district, and quarter, represented by binomial data likelihood contributions. Cost data will comprise the mean and standard deviation of cost per child attending care, by country, district, and quarter of measurement, represented by gamma distribution data likelihood contributions. The regression component of the model will simultaneously represent: the logit-transformed probability of starting treatment, and the log-transformed mean cost per child attending care. The "random effects" for districts will be modelled as bivariate normal, with an LKJ (Lewandowski-Kurowicka-Joe distribution) prior used for its variance-covariance matrix. Trial arm and quarter will be treated as "fixed effects". We will estimate standard of care, intervention, and incremental treatment initiation rates and cost per 1,000 (for example) children with attending care in each country, incremental cost-effectiveness ratios as cost per additional child attending care initiated on TB

treatment, and undertake and report the separate stratified analyses laid out in Section 4.6. These analyses will be performed using *Stan* in R, with standard metrics such as R-hat used to assess adequate convergence. Standard of care and intervention treatment rates and costs will be modelled as counterfactuals for each district-quarter and aggregated weighted by the numbers of children presenting. Posterior samples for each analysis will be used to calculate uncertainty intervals, incremental cost-effectiveness ratios, and visualisations of cost-effectiveness acceptability curves and cost-effectiveness planes.

In the subsequent model-based analyses, the economic model will generate projections for mortality and morbidity which will be used to calculate the expected overall health outcomes for patients following each alternative intervention arm in terms of DALYs.

It is noted that the Global Burden of Disease disability weights are the same for adults and children, and so the weights that will be used for TB are not designed specifically for children. Due to the relatively short-term loss of quality of life due to each child having TB (typically treated for 6 months), and the large loss of length of life through dying from TB at a young age, the benefits of interventions that increase the diagnosis and successful treatment of TB are likely to be dominated by mortality benefits, and so uncertainty in the disability weights applied to children with TB is unlikely to make a notable difference to the DALY results. Therefore, we will generate both outcomes: DALYS and years of life lost.

The cost and DALY results from the model will then be combined to calculate ICER. ICERs will be presented in PPP US dollars (USD) per DALY averted. ICERs will be compared to the cost-effectiveness thresholds outlined in section 5.4. We will use cost-effectiveness acceptability curves graphs to summarise the impact of uncertainty on the ICER estimates in relation to possible values of the cost-effectiveness threshold. Cost-effectiveness and budget impact analyses will first be conducted for each country.

5.9 Analysis of budget impact

The budget impact of implementing the Decide-TB intervention will be calculated. This will take the additional costs and savings of implementing the intervention compared to current health spending for the standard of care, and apply these costs to whole populations. The costs will be valued as described in section 5.7, including the upfront cost of new infrastructure, equipment and training as well as the running costs of TB diagnosis and treatment services.

This will be evaluated first for the districts in which the studies are being conducted, and then projected nationally based on population, the number, size and type of existing health facilities, and reported TB incidence rates.

The speed of implementation assumed will be determined by expert opinion, based on the feasibility and precedents for rolling out large scale programme changes nationally in each of the study countries. This will be subject to sensitivity analysis to assess the impact if implementation is achieved more quickly or more slowly. Budget impact will be calculated over horizons of 1, 2 and 5 years. Costs will not be discounted and will be presented in both PPP USD and local currency.

Expert opinions and NTP expenses data will inform scenario analyses to estimate the financial amount and nature (cost inputs) of contributions from domestic (Ministry of Health) and external (e.g. The Global Fund) sources for scaling up the Decide-TB intervention.

5.10 Analysis of costs incurred to families

Analysis of cost data for patient families will be performed on R software. Descriptive statistics will be presented for demographic characteristics, clinical characteristics, clinical outcomes and costs for patient families in each country. Costs will be categorised into direct medical costs, direct non-medical costs and indirect costs, and are presented for the period before and during the Decide-TB intervention. The proportion of households facing catastrophic costs (TB management costs exceeding 20% of the annual pre-TB household income) can be adjusted for local effects (e.g. variation in costs by geographic area) using a logistic regression model with a binomial distribution and a logit link function including country and care model fixed effects. These proportions will be presented as model-predicted averages and 95% confidence intervals.

5.11 Subgroup analyses/Analysis of heterogeneity

Intervention results will be reported individually for each country. Additional analyses will be performed to investigate how cost-effectiveness varies between different patient subgroups (such as age): see Section 4.6.

5.12 Sensitivity Analyses

Sensitivity and scenario analyses will be performed to assess the robustness of results to selected assumptions.

The initial within-trial cost-effectiveness analysis will estimate the proportion of children on shorter regimens using data from the TB patient cost survey and extra opinion. Sensitivity analyses will explore the impact of different levels of shorter regimen use.

We will explore sensitivity to the assumption that no children lost to follow-up receive treatment with an analysis where they all do. Where interventions include children up to 15 years of age, we will report results stratified by under 5 years of age and above 5 years.

One-way sensitivity analysis will be performed to assess the impact that changes in certain key parameters (such as TB incidence, diagnostic accuracy or treatment completion rate) will have on model results. We will seek to identify and describe the strongest determinants of country-level cost-effectiveness and the greatest sources of uncertainty regarding cost-effectiveness for each intervention.

We will also assess in the sensitivity analysis the effect of accounting for health outcomes with and without post-TB sequelae on the cost-effectiveness of the intervention. We will also compute results without including post-TB impacts on health-related quality of life and long-term increased mortality due to TB.

If a change in adult TB diagnoses is observed, we will also produce results that include the changes in resource use and health benefits associated with treating TB in adults. We will model benefits to individuals using a case-fatality ratio approach, and approximate effects of reduced transmission using estimates over a single generation rather than by using a transmission model.

Section 6: Economic modelling analyses

The initial within-trial cost-effectiveness will not use decision analytic modelling. Subsequent model-based cost-utility analyses will, as described below.

6.1 Decision analytic modelling

Decision modelling will be used to evaluate the changes in costs and health on introducing the interventions. Modelling is necessary to extrapolate from study outcomes to morbidity and mortality outcomes, and to evaluate combined designs for the primary objective. Separate models will be constructed for each TDA (with shared natural history assumptions for common patient groups) and used for separate cost-effectiveness analyses for each study, before being combined to explore combined packages of interventions in each country. Natural history assumptions refer to case fatality rates calculated as the number of total deaths due to TB divided by the number of total TB cases over a lifetime horizon. Case fatality rates will be differentiated on whether the child is diagnosed with TB or not, and TB treated or not. Further information on this approach can be found in other published work (d'Elbée et al. 2024). We also intend to consider a notation on TB disease severity derived from the Decide-TB individual patient database (Work Package 3 of the Decide-TB project) to influence the estimation of our case fatality rates.

6.2 Model type

We use a decision tree approach which can effectively model complex patient care pathways, but are less suited to chronic conditions with repeated events. TB in children is a relatively acute condition, without onward transmission, for which costs and consequences essentially accrue in the present (understanding that loss of discounted life-years can be attached to TB deaths happening in the present). The decision analytic models will be developed as decision trees using the HEdtree R package version 1.0 (Dodd 2024) which allows probabilities for different routes out of each node, and for the costs, quality-of-life and delays for each node to depend arbitrarily on the characteristics (such as age or comorbidities) of patients moving through the decision tree (**Figure 3**). To model combined intervention packages, tree models representing individual study components will be 'plumbed' together (or exist in parallel for separate patient groups) with flows of patients through different pathways determined by their characteristics and the probabilities defining the intervention and comparator.

Fig. 1: Simplified patient care pathways for the diagnosis and treatment of tuberculosis in children *Clinical exam, and, for a proportion of patients, Xpert on sputum or gastric aspirate, smear microscopy and CXR (in DH). "Xpert" in the DH-focused and PHC-focused strategies means "Xpert Ultra on NPA & stool". We define "non-systematic assessment" as a step in the patient care pathway where a child presenting to the health facility may receive consideration for the possibility of having TB, depending on the clinician and patient. This screening may contain some of the components of our systematic screening and/or some form of clinical examination, but it would not be expected to follow the precise protocols that define the "systematic screening" and "clinical examination" in our intervention arms. TB, tuberculosis; DH, district hospital; PHC, primary health centre; CXR, chest X-ray.

Figure 3. Example of decision tree - cost-effectiveness analysis of the TB-Speed Decentralization study (Source: d’Elbée, eClinicalMedicine, 2024)

6.3 Model structure

A core model containing common evidence and functions for modelling TB natural history and outcomes (on and off treatment, and by age and comorbidity) has been created and is being maintained as an R package (Dodd 2019). This model is based on previously published work (Dodd et al. 2017, 2014, 2018), includes child age, sex, and HIV/ART status, and models the natural history of progression to TB disease and TB treatment outcomes. This will be extended to include TB treatment outcomes for children with SAM. The purpose of maintaining this core model as a package is to ensure consistency in natural history and outcome assumptions across individual models.

The models for each intervention will have structures determined by the patient pathways, and the events in these pathways where different outcomes are possible (such as facility visits, referral, screening, diagnostics, treatment initiation and treatment completion), and the points in pathways where resource use accrues. Regression models will be used to model costs and outcome probabilities as a function of patient characteristics so that intervention combinations that alter patient flows can be combined. Different types of facilities will be explicitly modelled. Initial conceptual models will be based on protocols, and iteratively refined in discussion with the trialists.

6.4 Treatment effect beyond the end of the trial

Recent studies show that respiratory tuberculosis has long-term impacts on healthcare utilisation beyond treatment (Romanowski et al. 2023). We will consider post-tuberculosis sequelae in the measure of DALYs accounting for post-tuberculosis health-related quality of life in children and long-term increased mortality due to TB. We will include a causal contribution of TB to long term decrements in health-related quality of life. We will review emerging evidence on child-specific evidence, and in the absence of improved evidence use published approaches (Menzies et al. 2021).

6.5 Other key assumptions

The model will not be dynamic (that is, accounting for indirect effects due to any reduction in TB transmission from infected children to other children or adults), due to the low risk of transmission from children with active TB (compared to the higher risk of transmission from adults with active TB). Insofar as this may slightly underestimate the true amount of transmission of TB, this is a conservative assumption, as it will understate the benefit of any intervention that identifies and successfully treats a larger proportion of children with TB than in current standard of care. We will use UN-estimated national life-tables to estimate discounted life-years lost. For children lost to follow-up, our default assumption will be that they all do not receive treatment; but in sensitivity analysis we will assume that they all receive treatment. Our use of a decision tree approach limits our ability to consider heterogeneity in resource use and any complex patterns of repeat interactions. However, we would not necessarily have the data to meaningfully describe such heterogeneity, and repeat interactions are typically limited in our settings for childhood TB ; we do allow for a single potential reassessment. Due to ethical considerations, and in common with other TB modelling, we rely on reviews of prechemotherapy literature to estimate untreated TB mortality (Jenkins et al. 2017). These cohorts may differ in important ways that limit their applicability to modern African children.

6.6 Methods for identifying and estimating parameters

The majority of parameters in the model will be characterised directly from the Decide-TB study or literature data.

Clinical effectiveness outcomes will be taken from the Decide-TB trial results. As many secondary endpoints of the studies as possible will also be integrated into the model or used to check the validity of the projected results.

Parameters governing progression to disease will be as in previous models, which were based on literature reviews. Mortality will be based on case fatality rates researched from literature reviews for the relevant populations.

For each study, the unit of modelling will reflect study design, with, for example, changes to cost and DALY outputs being aggregated to summary results using techniques that are as consistent as possible with those specified in the corresponding statistical analysis plans.

6.7 Model uncertainty

All model parameters will be modelled as random variables to capture uncertainty. To quantify the impact of parameter uncertainty on model results, probabilistic sensitivity analysis will be conducted on all uncertain parameters by simultaneously sampling each parameter 10,000 times from predefined probability distributions appropriate to the parameter modelled, to generate 10,000 estimates of incremental costs and benefits. Where regression models describing model steps are used to evaluate new configurations of intervention, prediction uncertainty will be included.

When extrapolating study results from studies that have not been evaluated in all countries to other countries, hierarchical models will be used to extrapolate results and quantify their uncertainty.

6.8 Model verification

Validation of our key outcome of mortality is not possible as following children known to have TB without treating them is unethical, and since this study is not powered or designed for a mortality end-point. For untreated TB we rely on systematic review of prechemotherapy paediatric cohorts (Jenkins et al. 2017). Therefore, the next best option is for us to conduct model verifications. All modelling code will be checked by at least two experienced modellers to find any errors in the code and to check for face validity of the model. Our modelling approach will be further verified during the peer review process of our economic evaluation for publication in scientific journals.

6.9 Value of Information analysis

The estimation of the value, in terms of cost and health outcomes, of collecting more data/information on key parameters influencing the results of the cost-effectiveness model will be assessed using an Expected Value of Perfect Information analysis. Given our probabilistic sensitivity analysis-based approach to assess model uncertainty, we will consider a non-parametric regression approach (Strong et al. 2014).

Section 7: Reporting and dissemination of results

7.1 Reporting standards

All data collected during this research are managed by the study sponsors (INS in Mozambique, UNZA in Zambia, University of Bordeaux as representatives of sponsors in the European Union). Individual-level datasets (e.g. individual patient cost dataset) will not be shared to a third party without the written consent of the sponsors as per study protocol. However aggregated datasets (e.g. at health facility level) will be available via online repository (GitHub) alongside scientific publications of the economic studies.

The results will be published after final analysis in the form of scientific articles in peer-reviewed journals, or presented at national and international conferences. To ensure respect of international standards for authorship, all publications must follow the rules contained in the publication charter defined by the Decide-TB project as part of the project communication plan. Any publication or communication (oral or written) is decided by mutual agreement between the coordinating investigators, the modelling/health economics investigators and the sponsors, and will respect the international recommendations (ICMJE 2024).

The mention of the origin of the funding, the authorizations of the competent authorities, and the consent of the participants must appear in the acknowledgments.

The CHEERS guidelines (Husereau et al. 2022) will be followed when reporting the health economic evaluation, in a format appropriate to stakeholders and policy makers.

7.2 Reporting deviations from the HEAP

Any substantial change or addition to this HEAP requires a written amendment to be approved by the coordinating investigators.

These requirements for approval should in no way prevent any immediate action from being taken by the investigators in the interests of preserving the safety of all study participants.

7.3 Dissemination of results and transfer to policy

A PhD student from the Decide-TB team, based at the NTP Zambia will be conducting research aiming to improve the use of economic evaluation evidence (here the findings from the Decide-TB project) by national decision makers. These will be done through the costing and budget impact modelling of the Decide-TB intervention accounting for a mixed funding environment, i.e. distinguishing between resources supported financially by the Ministry of Health and those by external donors (e.g. The Global Fund). We will also develop a conceptual framework aiming to better support health planners with TB financial planning and priority setting in LMICs with high TB burden. Finally, we plan to conduct a program budgeting marginal analysis (investment/disinvestment analysis) to inform the NTPs on how to improve the overall efficiency of their activities towards their objectives for TB control, including the adoption of the TDA-based approach for TB diagnosis.

Results from the economic evaluations will inform the NTP-led budgeting exercise related to the scale-up of the TDA-based approach in each country. Findings will also inform the revisions and operationalisation of the

country's national strategic plan (due to be revised in 2027 in Zambia and in 2029 in Mozambique). Finally, results also aim to inform the decision of national stakeholders about the amount of financial support and nature of contribution coming from the Ministries of Health and from external donors (e.g. The Global Fund).

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